
STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN RIVERINE SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN BAYELSA AND DELTA STATES: THE IMPACT OF FLOOD RISK ELEMENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the impact of flood risk elements on students' academic achievement in riverine secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta States. Three research questions were formulated and answered, and one hypothesis was raised and tested at the 0.05 alpha level. The study employed an ex-post-facto research design. The sample for the study consisted of 480 respondents from a population of 47,612. The instruments used for the study were the researcher-developed questionnaire titled the Flood Risk Elements Questionnaire (FREQ) and the Academic Achievement Proforma (AAP), both validated by two experts in Educational Administration and Foundations at Delta State University, Abraka. Data analysis employed mean, standard deviation, and the coefficient of determination to answer the research questions, while Pearson Moment Correlation was used to test the hypotheses. The findings of the study show that flood risk elements in riverine secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta States are high. The level of students' academic achievement in these schools is low. There is a significant relationship between flood risk elements and students' academic achievement in riverine secondary schools in both Bayelsa and Delta States. It was concluded, based on the findings, that flood risk elements such as slippery floors, unstable structures, poor air quality, and exposure to waterborne diseases are common in riverine secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta States. Consequently, students' academic achievement in these schools is low, and flood risks negatively affect their academic performance. It was recommended that the government and relevant stakeholders prioritize the construction and reinforcement of flood-resilient infrastructure in riverine secondary schools. This includes elevating school buildings, installing effective drainage systems, and using water-resistant materials to reduce structural deterioration and minimize flood damage.

Keywords: Flood Risk Elements, Academic Achievement, Riverine Secondary Schools

INTRODUCTION

Academic achievement is defined as the level of success that a student reaches in an academic setting. It includes activities such as classroom assignments, tests and exams, continuous assessment scores, school attendance percentage and any other activities connected to formal learning. Academic achievement can be measured by grades achieved in a particular course or subject area, standardized test results (Onofe-Overah, Egwunyenga, & Akpotu, 2023). Academic achievement is defined as the level of success a student has attained in an educational setting through the acquisition and application of knowledge, skills, and problem-solving abilities. Academic achievement can be measured using assessments such as tests or other evaluation methods like essay writing or presentations. Academic achievement typically reflects academic performance during class activities, attendance records, assessment scores (tests/exams), participation levels within classes, end-of-year grades and overall grade point average (Okagbare, Ossai, & Osadebe, 2023).

The academic achievement of riverine secondary school students has been a matter of great concern to educational stakeholders. This is due to fluctuation in the level of result being recorded year in year out. There are a number of factors that positive or negatively influence the academic achievement of riverine secondary school students. However, the factor of interest in this study are flood risk and flood management strategies. One of the primary reasons that stimulate interest in studying flood risk and flood management strategies in riverine secondary schools is the growing concern about environmental issues and the continuous decline in academic achievement of study in the area. Floods have become more frequent and severe due to climate change, leading to devastating consequences for communities living near rivers. As a result, there is a heightened urgency to develop effective flood management strategies to mitigate the impact of floods on riverine secondary schools.

“Flood risk elements” which is first variable of interest refers to the potential threats that accompany occurrence of flood in a particular area. It may also be defined as the potential consequences that are being experienced during flooding. This may range from potential loss of life, property damage, migration, and the disruption of academic calendars. Flood risk elements may also involve the assessment of various factors that contribute to the likelihood and severity of flooding. Flood risk is the probability of a flood event occurring, along with the potential adverse consequences it may have on people, infrastructure, and the environment. It encompasses both the likelihood and magnitude of flooding, taking into account factors such as rainfall patterns, topography, land use, and the effectiveness of flood mitigation measures (Umar & Gray, 2022). Flood risk elements is the result of combining the likelihood (probability) of a flood event occurring and the impact (repercussions) if it did. Flooding may cause severe damage to infrastructure and can displace individuals from their homes and businesses. As a result, individuals may be at risk of drowning or falling victim to other hazards associated with the flood event. Flood risk is a crucial concept that has gained increasing attention in recent years due to the growing frequency and severity of flooding events worldwide. According to Mansor, Mohamad & Shazwani (2019) flood risk refers to the potential for a specific area or community to experience flooding and the associated impacts, such as property damage, infrastructure disruption, and loss of life. Knowledge of flood risk elements are essential for effective disaster management and mitigation strategies, as it allows authorities and stakeholders to assess vulnerability, plan for emergency response, and implement measures to reduce the adverse effects of flooding. Scientists and researchers can determine the exact risk of flooding in a given area by analyzing historical data and applying sophisticated modeling techniques. This information can then be used to prioritize areas for preventive measures such as constructing flood barriers or improving drainage systems.

Statement of the Problem

Riverine areas are prone to frequent flooding due to their proximity to water bodies. Bayelsa and Delta States. The problem of flood risk elements in these states poses a significant challenge to the educational institutions situated in these areas, especially secondary schools. The constant threat of flooding has in various times cause academic setbacks to schools in Bayelsa and Delta States. The academic achievement of students is a crucial aspect of their educational journey. Flood risk elements in riverine secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta States may have a negative impact on students' academic achievement.

Despite the persistent threat to educational activities, particularly in riverine communities where secondary schools are highly susceptible., there is insufficient empirical research on how flood risk elements specifically affect students' academic achievement in these areas. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the extent to which flood risk elements influence students' academic performance in riverine secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta States.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What are the flood risk elements in riverine secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta States?
2. What is the level of students' academic achievement in riverine secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta States?
3. What is the relationship between flood risk elements and students' academic achievement in riverine secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta states?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were raised to guide the study:

1. There is no significant relationship between flood risk elements and students' academic achievement in riverine secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta states.

Methodology

This study adopted an ex-post facto research design utilizing a correlational method. The population for the study consisted of 47,612 teachers and students from 315 public secondary schools located in the riverine areas of Bayelsa and Delta States. Of this total, 18,776 individuals (comprising 15,044 students and 3,732 teachers) were from Bayelsa State, while 28,836 individuals (comprising 27,085 students and 1,751 teachers) were from Delta State. Data on the population were obtained from the Bayelsa State Ministry of Education (2023) and the Delta State Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education (2023). From this population, a total of 480 respondents, including 240 students and 240 teachers, were selected from 48 public secondary schools in the riverine Local Government Areas (LGAs) of both Bayelsa and Delta States using a multi-stage sampling technique. In the first stage, four riverine LGAs were randomly selected from each state, for a total of eight LGAs. In the second stage, six public secondary schools were purposively selected from each LGA, with a focus on schools that had recurring flood experiences. In the third stage, five teachers and five SS2 students were randomly chosen from each of the 48 selected schools.

Two instruments were employed for data collection: The Flood Risk Elements Questionnaire (FREQ) and the Academic Achievement Proforma (AAP). The FREQ consists of 20 items that assess flood risk elements on a 4-point scale ranging from Very High Extent (VHE) to Low Extent (LE), adapted from the works of Scaini et al. (2021) and Shah et al. (2022). The AAP collected SS2 third-term exam results from the 2019–2023 academic sessions. To ensure the validity of the instruments, face and content validity were conducted.

Experts from the Department of Educational Management and Foundations at Delta State University reviewed and refined the questionnaire. Factor analysis was carried out using responses from 50 teachers in Akuku-Toru LGA, Rivers State, which resulted in a cumulative variance explained of 70.13% for the Flood Risk Elements. To assess the reliability of the FREQ, Cronbach's Alpha was used with data from the same 50 teachers, yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.821. The researcher and five trained assistants administered the questionnaire directly to the respondents in the sampled schools. Teachers completed the questionnaire, while the students' exam results were obtained from the form teachers using the AAP. The collected data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation, coefficient of determination (R^2), and Pearson Product Moment Correlation ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Results and Discussion

Research Question 1: What are the flood risk elements in riverine secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta States?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation on flood risk elements in riverine secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta States

S/N	Flood risk elements	Bayelsa			Delta			Both States		
		M	SD	D	M	SD	D	M	SD	D
	Slippery floors	3.08	.73	+	3.03	.91	+	3.05	.83	+
	Submerged electronic outlets,	3.22	.59	+	2.98	.89	+	3.09	.77	+
	Unstable structures	3.05	.61	+	2.95	.90	+	3.00	.77	+
	Risks of slips,	3.10	.68	+	2.93	.84	+	3.01	.77	+
	Risks of ripping,	3.15	.65	+	2.91	.87	+	3.03	.78	+
	Risks of falling	3.09	.63	+	2.84	.83	+	2.96	.75	+
	Electrical accidents.	3.00	.62	+	2.94	.86	+	2.97	.75	+
	Structural deterioration,	3.14	.70	+	2.89	.92	+	3.01	.83	+
	Structural decay,	3.21	.63	+	2.96	.91	+	3.08	.80	+
	Compromised building integrity.	3.09	.64	+	2.77	.92	+	2.92	.81	+
	Loss of educational materials	3.19	.65	+	2.86	.89	+	3.01	.80	+
	Health and death risks to students and staff	3.08	.75	+	2.84	.92	+	2.95	.85	+
	Poor indoor air quality issues,	3.07	.69	+	2.83	.89	+	2.95	.81	+
	Respiratory problems	3.15	.74	+	2.84	.89	+	2.99	.83	+
	Allergic reactions in the classroom.	3.06	.63	+	2.80	.84	+	2.93	.76	+
	Disruptions to classes	3.07	.53	+	2.68	.88	+	2.87	.76	+
	Damage to school equipment	3.09	.62	+	2.74	.86	+	2.90	.77	+
	Waterborne diseases	3.09	.57	+	2.75	.84	+	2.91	.74	+
	Injuries resulting from exposure to contaminated floodwaters	3.11	.75	+	2.87	.80	+	2.98	.78	+
	Emotional distress impacting mental health and well-being	3.00	.96	+	2.69	1.07	+	2.83	1.03	+
	Average Mean Score	3.10	.67	+	2.86	.89	+	2.97	.80	+

Keys: M = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, R= Remark, + = Agree, - = Disagree

Data in Table 1 shows mean and standard deviation on flood risk elements in riverine secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta States. The result revealed that respondents from Bayelsa State agree on all the items with mean scores above 2.50. Also, respondents from Delta State agree on all the items with mean scores above 2.50. When both States were combined, respondents agree with mean scores of 3.05, 3.09, 3.00, 3.01, 3.03, 2.96, 2.97, 3.01, 3.08, 2.92, 3.01, 2.95, 2.95, 2.99, 2.93, 2.87, 2.90, 2.91, 2.98, 2.83 on slippery floors, submerged electronic outlets, unstable structures, risks of slips, risks of ripping, risks of falling, electrical accidents, structural deterioration, structural decay, compromised building integrity, loss of educational materials, health and death risks to students and staff, poor

indoor air quality issues, respiratory problems, allergic reactions in the classroom, disruptions to classes, damage to school equipment, waterborne diseases, injuries resulting from exposure to contaminated floodwaters and emotional distress impacting mental health and well-being respectively.

Thus, flood risk elements in riverine secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta States includes; slippery floors, submerged electronic outlets, unstable structures, risks of slips, risks of ripping, risks of falling, electrical accidents, structural deterioration, structural decay, compromised building integrity, loss of educational materials, health and death risks to students and staff, poor indoor air quality issues, respiratory problems, allergic reactions in the classroom, disruptions to classes, damage to school equipment, waterborne diseases, injuries resulting from exposure to contaminated floodwaters and emotional distress impacting mental health and well-being.

Research Question 2: What is the level of students’ academic achievement in riverine secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta States?

Table 2: Percentage on level of students’ academic achievement in riverine secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta States

Students’ Academic Achievement	Bayelsa				Delta				Both States			
	No of Pass	% of Pass	No of Fail	% of Fail	No of Pass	% of Pass	No of Fail	% of Fail	No of Pass	% of Pass	No of Fail	% of Fail
2019	386	29.4	927	70.6	268	20.9	1016	79.1	654	25.2	1943	74.8
2020	384	29.2	929	70.8	262	20.2	1034	79.8	646	24.8	1963	75.2
2021	403	30.7	910	69.3	306	25.8	879	74.2	709	28.4	1789	71.6
2022	432	32.9	881	67.1	263	20.5	1018	79.5	695	26.8	1899	73.2
2023	442	33.7	871	66.3	275	21.4	1008	78.6	717	27.6	1879	72.4
Total	2047	31.2	4518	68.8	1374	21.7	4955	78.3	3421	26.5	9473	73.5

Table 2 reveals that students' academic achievement in riverine secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta States from 2019 to 2023 shows consistently high fail rates, with only slight improvements over the years. Bayelsa has a higher overall pass rate (31.2%) than Delta (21.7%), though both states maintain a majority of failing students, with Bayelsa's fail rate dropping from 70.6% in 2019 to 66.3% in 2023 and Delta's remaining near 79%. Combined, the states have an average pass rate of 26.5% and fail rate of 73.5%. This trend implies that the level of students’ academic achievement in riverine secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta States is low.

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between flood risk elements and students’ academic achievement in riverine secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta states?

Table 3: Relationship between flood risk elements and students’ academic achievement

Variable	Bayelsa		Delta		Bayelsa& Delta		r	r ²	r ² %	Remark
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD				
Flood risk elements	61.15	7.10	56.89	10.67	58.93	9.37	.804	.646	64.6	Positive relationship
Students’ academic achievement	8.70	1.86	8.44	2.26	8.57	2.08				

Data in Table 3 shows the between flood risk elements and students’ academic achievement in riverine secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta states. The result shows

Bayelsa State have a mean score of 61.15, SD = 7.10 for flood risk elements and mean score of 8.70, SD= 1.86 for students' academic achievement. Also, Delta State have a mean score of 56.89, SD = 10.67 for flood risk elements and mean score of 8.44, SD= 2.26 for students' academic achievement. When both States were combined, they have a mean score of 58.93, SD = 9.37 for flood risk elements and mean score of 8.57, SD= 2.08 for students' academic achievement. The computed r value of .804 shows that there is a positive relationship between flood risk elements and students' academic achievement in riverine secondary school in Bayelsa and Delta States. The r^2 value of .646 revealed that flood risk elements relate to students' academic achievement in riverine secondary school in Bayelsa and Delta States by 64.6%

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between flood risk elements and students' academic achievement in riverine secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta states.

Table 4: Pearson r between flood risk elements and students' academic achievement

		Floods Risk Elements	Students' Academic Achievement
Floods Risk Elements	Pearson Correlation	1	.804**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	460	460
Students' Academic Achievement	Pearson Correlation	.804**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	460	2610

** Significant at 0.05

Table 4 revealed the Pearson r between flood risk elements and students' academic achievement. The table shows a significant relationship with r value of .804 and significance $p=.000$. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between flood risk elements and students' academic achievement in riverine secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta states was rejected. Thus, there is a significant relationship between flood risk elements and students' academic achievement in riverine secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta states.

Discussion of Results

Flood Risk Elements in Riverine Secondary Schools

Flood risk elements in riverine secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta States includes; slippery floors, submerged electronic outlets, unstable structures, risks of slips, risks of ripping, risks of falling, electrical accidents, structural deterioration, structural decay, compromised building integrity, loss of educational materials, health and death risks to students and staff, poor indoor air quality issues, respiratory problems, allergic reactions in the classroom, disruptions to classes, damage to school equipment, waterborne diseases, injuries resulting from exposure to contaminated floodwaters and emotional distress impacting mental health and well-being.

The identified flood risk elements in riverine secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta States, such as slippery floors, unstable structures, and submerged outlets, are largely attributed to the geographical and environmental characteristics of these regions. Located in low-lying riverine areas, these schools are particularly vulnerable to seasonal and occasional flooding, which is exacerbated by climate change and poor drainage infrastructure. Flood waters can infiltrate buildings, weakening structural components and creating hazardous

conditions. The absence of adequate flood defenses or drainage systems leaves school facilities exposed, causing deterioration of walls, floors, and electrical systems, all of which compromise building integrity and safety. Additionally, health-related risks, including respiratory issues, allergic reactions, and waterborne diseases, stem from prolonged exposure to standing water and contaminated floodwaters. The infiltration of water and subsequent growth of mold and mildew within school buildings lead to poor indoor air quality, directly impacting the health of students and staff. Emotional distress among students and teachers may arise from frequent disruptions and unsafe learning environments, further affecting mental health. Collectively, these elements pose severe physical, health, and psychological challenges, which undermine the well-being and safety of the school community.

Flood risk elements in riverine secondary schools, including slippery floors, unstable structures, and submerged outlets, create hazardous conditions for students and staff. These elements have been found to compromise safety, learning continuity, and infrastructure integrity. Olorunfemi and Raheem (2013) found that in flood-prone areas in Nigeria, school buildings suffered from structural decay due to frequent exposure to water, leading to unsafe environments that increased risks of accidents. Similarly, Adedeji and Olaniyan (2016) observed that poorly maintained schools in flood zones had more frequent structural issues and electrical hazards, such as submerged outlets, which heightened the risk of injuries among students and staff. Additionally, Aboagye et al. (2018) studied the impact of flooding on Ghanaian schools and reported health concerns, including respiratory issues from damp environments and waterborne diseases caused by contaminated floodwaters. Emotional stress and anxiety due to unsafe conditions further impact students' mental health and well-being, which Uitto (2014) noted could decrease students' engagement and focus in the classroom, ultimately affecting learning outcomes.

Level of Students' Academic Achievement in Riverine Secondary Schools

The level of students' academic achievement in riverine secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta States is low. The low academic achievement observed among students in flood-prone schools in Bayelsa and Delta States is a direct consequence of the unsafe and unstable learning environments. Frequent flooding disrupts the school calendar, leading to unplanned closures, interruptions in the curriculum, and loss of instructional time. For students, inconsistent schooling affects their ability to follow lesson plans, complete assignments, and prepare adequately for examinations, ultimately resulting in lower academic performance. Moreover, health issues caused by exposure to flood-related risks further contribute to absenteeism and reduced concentration. Students affected by respiratory issues, allergies, and mental health challenges may find it difficult to engage fully in academic activities. The physical environment also plays a significant role; students in structurally compromised and uncomfortable classrooms are less likely to remain motivated and focused. These environmental stressors compound the educational challenges faced by students, limiting their potential for academic success. The low academic achievement in flood-affected schools can be attributed to disruptions, health challenges, and psychological stress associated with flooding. Desforges and Abouchaar (2003) found that disruptions to school routines and extended absenteeism due to environmental challenges, such as floods, hindered students' academic performance and limited syllabus coverage. Ajibade et al. (2013) further linked health issues caused by waterborne diseases to increased absenteeism, which undermines students' ability to perform consistently. In a study on Tanzanian schools, Ngware et al. (2013) highlighted that inadequate infrastructure and frequent closures significantly reduced students' engagement and academic outcomes. These findings suggest that the continual impact of flood hazards in Bayelsa and Delta States undermines both academic consistency

and overall performance, as students face challenges that limit their participation in a stable learning environment.

Flood Risk Elements and Students' Academic Achievement

There is a significant relationship between flood risk elements and students' academic achievement in riverine secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta states. The significant relationship between flood risk elements and students' academic achievement in riverine secondary schools highlights how environmental hazards directly disrupt students' learning experiences. When schools are frequently exposed to flooding, structural and environmental risks such as slippery floors, damaged electrical outlets, unstable buildings, and poor air quality make the learning environment unsafe and uncomfortable. These hazards lead to higher absenteeism rates, as both students and teachers may be physically unable to attend or feel unsafe within the school premises. Flood-induced health problems, such as respiratory issues and allergies, further impact students' attendance and concentration. The resulting disruptions and health issues limit students' ability to perform well academically. Thus, schools that lack a resilient infrastructure or risk management systems leave students vulnerable to the negative effects of flooding, adversely affecting their educational outcomes.

The relationship between flood risk elements and students' academic achievement in riverine areas of Bayelsa and Delta States aligns with findings in similar studies. Floods often damage essential infrastructure, including classrooms, libraries, and sanitation facilities, hindering students' access to educational resources and disrupting academic schedules. Amadi (2013) found that in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni, Rivers State, school attendance significantly dropped during floods due to inaccessibility, leading to learning interruptions. Additionally, Chipso (2014) in Zimbabwe observed that floods increased absenteeism, delayed syllabus coverage, and impacted children's well-being, further lowering academic performance. In India, Gangadhar and Tatwa (2017) reported damage to school buildings, contamination of drinking water, and compromised hygiene during floods, which posed health risks to students and led to frequent school closures, affecting learning outcomes. Eimuhi & Ogedegbe, (2016) found that these disruptions affect students' psychological well-being, ultimately lowering engagement and achievement levels.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that flood risk elements—such as slippery floors, submerged electrical outlets, unstable structures, poor indoor air quality, and exposure to waterborne diseases—are prevalent in riverine secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta States. These flood-related hazards are primarily due to the schools' locations in low-lying, flood-prone areas. The presence of these hazards significantly compromises the physical safety, health, and emotional well-being of both students and staff, thereby creating an unstable and unsafe learning environment. It was also concluded that the level of students' academic achievement in these schools is low. Furthermore, it was established that flood risk elements have a negative impact on students' academic achievement in riverine secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta States.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations have been profound:

1. Government and relevant stakeholders should prioritize the construction and reinforcement of flood-resilient infrastructure in riverine secondary schools. This includes elevating school buildings, installing effective drainage systems, and using

water-resistant materials to reduce structural deterioration and minimize flood damage.

2. Schools should develop and adopt comprehensive flood preparedness and emergency response plans. This may involve regular risk assessments, evacuation drills, health and safety training for staff and students, and the provision of first-aid and sanitary facilities to manage health-related risks.
3. To mitigate the academic and psychological effects of flooding, targeted academic interventions such as make-up classes, flexible school calendars, and learning recovery programs should be introduced. In addition, schools should provide counseling services to support the emotional well-being and mental health of students affected by flood-related disruptions.

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